

Achieving New Exsport Brand Equity through Improvement of Social Media Marketing Effort (SMME) to Increase Sales

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ABSTRACT: The creative industry in Indonesia is currently in the spotlight because it contributes significant value to the economy in Indonesia. Therefore, bags brand also plays an increasingly important role in Indonesia's manufacturing sector and bags industry is one of creative economy in Indonesia. But, fashion industry need more than just only good quality product or good design product, to compete in nowadays, a brand must develop their customer relationship followed by the brand perception. Developing a dynamic and competitive business world demands the company to changes the orientation to the way they create the product, maintain its products, attract customers, and handle competitors. A deep understanding of how product information of a brand competes in the minds of consumers in the intense market competition is very crucial. This research will be used to create a marketing plan for the Exsport bags brand. The study utilized to produce the alternative approach is based on observations of the brand's internal and external analysis. The qualitative technique, and TOWS analysis are used in the strategy analysis. The qualitative method is used to assess existing market knowledge, which will lead to the identification of new brand value after rebranding, where TOWS analysis will define numerous potential strategies based on external and internal brand analysis. The strategy developed by this research focus on developing a new online media strategy to showcase Exsport's new value, as well as the relevant strategy used by the firm to compete in the future market.

KEYWORDS: Branding, Brand Equity, Creative Industry, Marketing, Social Media, Strategy.

INTRODUCTION

The bags industry plays an increasingly important role in Indonesia's manufacturing sector and bags industry is one of creative economy in Indonesia. The creative industry in Indonesia is currently in the spotlight because it contributes significant value to the economy in Indonesia. Based on data from the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, the contribution of the creative economy to Indonesia's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2018 was 7.16%. In fact, based on the 2020 Focus Economy Outlook data, the creative economy is able to contribute IDR 1,100 trillion to Indonesia's GDP throughout 2020 and now the contribution of Indonesia's creative economy to GDP was in the top three in the world after Hollywood and K-pop. But, fashion industry need more than just only good quality product or good design product, to compete in nowadays, a brand must develop their customer relationship followed by the brand perception. Developing a dynamic and competitive business world demands the company to changes the orientation to the way they create the product, maintain its products, attract customers, and handle competitors (Keller, K. L., & Kotler, P., 2009).

Nowadays, several Indonesia brands have been successful historically because they brought a quality product or service to market at the right time and continued to deliver it. Doing business in the current environment entails not only dealing with direct or indirect competitors, but also dealing with increased customer pressure. However, customer attitudes always demand and require change, and brands must keep an eye to succeed. Nowadays, many companies or organizations that have recognized the importance of customer-oriented marketing activities (Wang, Y., & Pizam, A., 2011). Customers are considered important because they determine survival of a company. A deep understanding of how product information of a brand competes in the minds of consumers in the intense market competition is very crucial.

Exsport is a life style brand that manufactures various bags as the core products and accessories. The company began as a small firm producing various styles of school bags in 1956 which then began its journey to a larger market in 1979. Exsport was established in 1979 and was initially launched under the Exxon brand before being renamed Exsport. Exsport has worked hard to create a

timeless product with a keen eye for detail and always redefining design through careful innovation and collaboration. With distinctive colors and designs, the Exsport market is aimed at young people, particularly young women.

On its journey, Exsport changed its logo 8 times starting from 1979 to 2021. During the Exsport journey from 1979 to 2015, the market that is covered by exports is young women and young men with product designs that are more inclined to male characters. Furthermore, in 2014, Exsport as a fashionable bag brand finally considered in shifting the company to focus on women’s fashion. And after all, in 2021 when the rebranding was carried out, Exsport established itself to be an independent female brand. Then on the last rebranding on 2021, the brand changes their tagline to “Bring Your Self Out” and also the brand logo.

Moreover, the rebranding process carried out in 2021 aims to expand market reach and updating the brand identity as an improvement effort to increase brand awareness. This is Exsport's new journey to tap into this modern era and become relevant to its customers. Along with that, Exsport took steps to not only provide backpacks for school bags but also by adding new product category variants, consisting of sports bags and more intense traveling or outdoor bags. The motive for the addition of this product line is because Exsport sees an opportunity to accommodate other product lines based on the activities and needs of the Indonesian market. In addition, the initiation of the widening of this product category is also one of Exsport's efforts to be able to survive during the COVID-19 Pandemic where the intensity of a person to go to school and work is very limited.

Based on Exsport internal data, in 2017 to 2019, before COVID-19 pandemic, the graph shows a stagnant sales achievement against Exsport actual targets. In other word, the stagnant sales growth was happening before Exsport do rebranding. In 2020 at pandemic situation is the lowest sales achievement among other years. On June 2021, Exsport start to launch their rebranding products and the graphs shows a slight increase. Furthermore, 2021 to 2022 line graphs, the actual sales growth against the target only reached

the peak in September in 2021 and July in 2022. From the general point of view, the Exsport sales performance after rebranding has not had a significant growth, even though the consumer activity has been running normally and based on secondary data in the background sub-chapter which shows the highest increase in travel and other outdoor activities even though Exsport providing much more categories than the Exsport before the rebranding.

Referring to the theory about the product life cycle, when the product has reached the decline phase, it means that the market becomes saturated at this phase, and the demand for the product and hence sales start to witness a reduction in demand and sales. This happened in the Exsport case and was exacerbated by a situation where not only Exsport's brand was losing relevance and needed brand revitalization, but also Exsport's internal and external brand perceptions were not aligned considering that Exsport had carried out a process of replacing brand identity in an adjacent period which made customers confused. Therefore, the two points above are suspected as the cause of the decline in sales at Export from year to year. Thus, from the information above, it can be said that the indication of the slow-moving sales of the new export non-school bag product line is due to the fast distribution of product without strengthening their brand perception as a lifestyle brand through product variant information chain to customer and Export requires improvement on the marketing strategies in how to implement an effective communication to their customer.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Rebranding

Based on Muzellec and Lambkin (2006), there are two description refer to rebranding words. First, it referring to changes in marketing aesthetics where there is a progression in rebranding, from the incremental modification of logos and slogans to the revolutionary creation of a new name (Stuart and Muzellec, 2004). Based on Marrilees and Miller (2008) on their journal study, the managerial implications highlight the importance of maintaining core brand values while remaining relevant to contemporary needs. The findings highlight the importance of a company fully understanding and preserving its core values. A corporation needs focus on a number of factors in order to successfully rebrand itself, including brand repositioning, brand renaming, brand redesign, and brand relaunching (recommunicating) (Goi Mei Teh, 2009). Furthermore, according to Keller (2013), repositioning alters the company's image in order to gain new values and positions in the minds of stakeholders. Then, redesigning entails making substantial changes to the company name, tagline, and logo across all aspects of the business, including office supplies, brochures, advertisements, annual reports, offices, and delivery vehicles, which are tangible representations of the position the company seeks to occupy. Finally, stakeholders are informed about the relaunch in order to raise awareness of the new name, tagline, or logo and speed up the adoption of the modifications.

- (1) Brand repositioning, this process is considered more dynamic because it is an additional process which must always be adjusted at any time to always be ready with changes in market trends and competitive pressures in wider external events. Brand positioning is done to change consumer perceptions.
- (2) Brand renaming is the most comprehensive and the riskiest in the rebranding process. Renaming is the stage where the new name becomes the media to send a strong signal to all stakeholders that the company or brand is changing strategy, changing focus, or changing ownership structure.
- (3) Brand redesign is redesigning the logo, style and message along with creating a new brand image. Name, slogan, and logo are important elements in designing a brand, because it is the company's need to build mission and values in the rebranding process.
- (4) Brand recommunicating is reporting or notification of a new brand within the company's internal and external. Internally, this can be done using brochures or bulletins, internal meetings, as well as workshops or the internet. Whereas externally, it can be through press releases, advertising to attract attention to the new brand and also facilitate the process of adopting the new name to stakeholders.

B. Social Media Marketing Effort (SMME)

One of the most effective ways for many organizations to connect with and entrust their customers to develop distinctive brand identity is through social media. It's because social media offers businesses incredible chances to connect with customers in their social networks and develop more intimate connections with them (Kelly, Kerr, & Drennan, 2010). Along with the rapid development of social media, the majority of lifestyle and fashion brands have realized that excluding SMMEs from the

marketing strategy would shows a negative brand ability to maintain a competitive edge. Social media have altered how brand material is produced, shared, and consumed, giving consumers' online relationships and content the ability to form brand perceptions instead of marketers anymore (Tsai & Men, 2013). Moreover, Social media marketing is "the use of social media technology, channels, and software to produce, communicate, distribute, and trade offers that have value for an organization's stakeholders," according to Tuten and Solomon (2017).

Based on how consumers perceive luxury goods, Kim and Ko (2012) divided SMMEs into five categories: entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, and word-of-mouth (WoM). SMMEs are unique since they immerse business organizations with dynamism. Additionally, they also help businesses by enhancing their brand value.

- (1) Interaction, social media may help customers and provide a forum for discussion and the sharing ideas. Muntinga et al. (2011) define social interaction as users who participate in platforms for brands on social media in order to connect with people who share their interests, engage in conversation, and discuss certain goods or brands with them.
- (2) Trendiness, in addition to being important conduits for product searches, social media also offers the most recent news and trending conversation topics (Naaman, Becker, & Gravano, 2011). As people view social media as a more reliable source of information than corporate-sponsored communication through conventional promotional activities, consumers are increasingly using it to get information (Mangold & Faulds, 2009; Vollmer & Precourt, 2008).
- (3) Customization, Brands may modify and exhibit personality by customizing their website, increasing brand connection and loyalty (Martin & Todorov, 2010). Customization in the context of social media refers to the target audience of the uploaded messages. A tailored message and a broadcast are the two sorts of postings (Zhu and Chen, 2015), depending on how personalized the messages are.
- (4) Word of Mouth (E-WOM), Social media connects online consumer-to-consumer brand interactions with eWOM (Muntinga et al., 2011). According to research, eWOM has more trust, empathy, and relevance for consumers than marketer-made online information sources (Gruen, Osmonbekov, & Czaplewski, 2006). Social media are the best platforms for eWOM since users may freely create and disseminate information about brands to their friends, peers, and other contacts (Kim & Ko, 2012).

C. Brand Equity

Organizations that decide to undertake a rebranding change typically want to increase brand equity (Goi & Goi, 2011). According to Baalbaki and Guzmán (2016), brand equity is a crucial term in marketing, management, and branding studies since it frequently translates into larger cash flows and enhanced competitiveness (Yoo, Donthu, & Lee, 2000). If the brand's name or symbol should change, some or all of the assets or liabilities might be harmed and even lost, although some may be moved to a new name and symbol (Aaker, 1991). The primary objective and difficulty of a rebranding strategy, according to Muzellec and Lambkin (2006), is to successfully build or transfer brand equity by transferring favorable associations to the redesigned brand while developing new ones.

- (1) Brand Awareness, refers to the level of consumer recognition, acceptance, and recall of a brand in any case (Percy and Rossiter, 1992). Where the brand awareness is also the ability of a potential buyer to recognize or recall that brand is a member of a certain product category (Aaker, 1991). Brand awareness could track or crowd power in consumer memories that reflect consumer's ability to remember or recognize a brand in different condition (Keller, 2009). Therefore, brand awareness is consisting of four levels which are brand recognition, brand recall, top of mind brand and dominant brand.
- (2) Perceived Quality, according to Aaker (1996), perceived quality is one of the primary factors of brand equity, and perceived quality is an important part of research in analyzing brand equity. Perceived quality is defined as customers' overall assessment of the brilliance and quality of a product or service about a competitor's offering. Perceived quality adds value by giving customers a cause to buy, distinguishing the brand, generating channel member interest, serving as the foundation for line extensions, and justifying a higher price (Aaker, 2006). Perceived quality refers to a consumer's assessment of how well a certain product will match their expectations.
- (3) Brand Association, according to Aaker (1991), brand association and brand equity are inextricably linked since brand association improves a brand's memorableness. According to Keller (1998), brand association may be formed by

associating it with attitudes, traits, and advantages. Brand association may also be used to acquire information (van Osselaer & Janiszewski, 2001) in order to carry out brand differentiation and brand extension (Aaker, 1996).

- D.** Purchase Intention is a kind of decision-making that studies the reason to buy a particular brand by consumer (Shah et al., 2012). Purchase intention also define as a situation where consumer tends to buy a certain product in certain condition. Customers purchase decision is a complex process. Purchase intention usually is related to the behavior, perceptions and attitudes of consumers. Purchase behavior is a key point for consumers to access and evaluate the specific product. Previous studies have proposed six stages before deciding to buy the product, which are: awareness, knowledge, interest, preference, persuasion and purchase (Kotler & Armstrong, 2010). Intent to purchase is a kind of decision in which studied why a customer purchases a brand in particular. Constructs like considering something purchasing a brand and anticipating to purchase a brand aids to scope the intentions of purchasing (Porter, 1974). Porter (1974) also elaborated customers' intention to purchase a focused brand is not merely by his same brand attitude, but also by his attitudes leading to other brands in choice of set considered.

METHOD

This study applies marketing research, which is the systematic and objective identification, collection, analysis, dissemination, and use of information for the purpose of improving decision making related to the identification and solution of problems and opportunities in marketing (Malhotra, N.K., 2012). To compete on these intents competition in a fast paced era, Exsport must be able to develop and improve their marketing strategy. The objective of a strategy is to optimize an organization's fundamental strengths while reducing risk in a current market (Kim, 2009). The study design begins with defining the brand problem being focused on the research subjective. Then to strengthen the development of the case study solution, it is important to conduct literature review which also be a theoretical based to the conceptual framework. The following stage is to define research technique, what data needs to be obtained, data collecting methods and then study design also has to be created. On this study itself, the research design consists of qualitative research. qualitative research aims to give insights and knowledge of the issue setting, quantitative research seeks to quantify the data and often employs some type of statistical analysis. Furthermore, the next step is to analyze the business situation where it includes the external analysis and internal analysis of the industry. Then the report of data collection and business analysis would be elaborated on business strategy formulation using SWOT and TOWS analysis so it could provide the output in a form of business solution alternatives and business strategies implementation.

A focus group is an interview with a small group of respondents that is conducted in an unstructured and natural manner by a trained moderator (Malhotra, N.K., 2011). The primary goal of focus groups is to gain insights by listening to a group of people from the relevant target market discuss issues of interest to the researcher. This FGD would be conduct in two different group of respondents. The first FGD is to involve internal Exsport management members which are Brand owner, General Manager, Exsport Marketing Lead, and Exsport Social Media Specialist to explore data and information that would lead to the research question and objectives. To get customer point of view to Exsport brand, The goal on FGD is to discuss with Exsport customer to get extensive information about what customers genuinely think of the brand through the brand exploration. The brand exploratory is study aimed at learning what customers believe and feel about the brand, as well as how they act toward it, in order to better identify the sources of brand equity and any potential impediments (Keller, 2013).

The result of the FGD will generate a customer knowledge about how far customer awareness against Exsport rebranding by recent Exsport's communication through their social media activity. Then, researcher will formulate the propose of media social communication strategy to deliver Exsport new brand equity as a lifestyle bag brand. Afterwards, the researcher will construct the list of questions related to the result of FGD that will be distributed via questionnaire to 200 respondents.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Internal Team Interview and Customer Focus Group Discussion

Advertising and digital marketing may be used to raise awareness and build interest in a product or service in order to successfully reach and engage with Exsport target consumer. This includes the use of various channels such as Exsport paid media, owned media, earned media and content marketing.

Overall, the data suggests that the respondents shows a positive attitude towards Exsport brand and its products. Most of them tend to learn the brand and buy the product via online platforms, but they are not aware of changes in brand identity such as logos and mottos, causing respondents to be ignorant of the vision and mission of the new Exsport brand, the knowledge of respondents is only limited to changing targets market and product identity changes. Most of the respondents thought that they had an interest in buying Exsport products but Exsport had not become the top of mind of the respondents when they needed a bag even though Exsport provided various product variants grouped by activity. In addition, the new Exsport branding is considered to be able to provide a perceived coolness to the wearer. However, the respondents have not been able to feel the maximum euphoria and experience because the standard offline Exsport shop has not yet spread which visualizes the new branding, they have not even been informed about the store with the distribution of new branding products, which means that effort is still needed on social media to communicate it.

The data also suggest that the respondent are receptive to marketing effort through social media like Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, and Youtube. They are attracted to fashion and lifestyle product through those channels and are concern not only with the product price but also the credibility of the brand of Exsport. The large number of influencers or societies that use Exsport is the most effective trigger that can initiate respondents to find out about the Exsport brand and buy it. Both offline word of mouth and E-WOM are important aspects in the respondent deciding which product to buy.

B. TOWS Matrix Analysis

In addition to the analysis of respondents' responses, the author also examines business solutions through the TOWS matrix analysis. In the TOWS analysis made, there are several 6 alternative action plans that can be implemented as a form of business solution to the problems faced by the Exsport brand.

- (1) Improving social media traffics and engagement by optimizing Exsport key digital media strategies
- (2) Do re-compositioning of specific content pillar on every Exsport social media platform
- (3) Increase lifestyle association through a collaboration with lifestyle brand with offline and online activation
- (4) Grow brand audience by listening and monitoring market keyword, phrases, or hash tags and carry out key phrase analysis
- (5) Comprehend the brand's positioning and proposition
- (6) Build national and regional through online media network to gain more brand awareness of new Exsport trust and reputation
- (7) Improve customer relation through developing membership program
- (8) Strengthen new Exsport brand identity through strong story telling
- (9) Cost leadership strategy by conducting signature, regular, and seasonal product
- (10) Be more transparent with customer about Exsport ideation and innovation process in a form of brand story telling
- (11) Improving interactive digital experience on offline store
- (12) Gradually shift and escalate customer centric strategy by achieving market, product and website MVP
- (13) Improving product line list and quantity stock planning based on comprehensive product performance data review
- (14) Create experience marketing which relevant with audience interest

C. Social Media Marketing Effort Strategy

Based on both addressed issues on customer analysis and TOWS matrix analysis that has been identified for Exsport, a marketing strategy solution might include the following elements:

- (1) Leverage and improving Exsport owned social media and increase collaboration on paid media and earned media From the elaboration of customer analysis and SWOT analysis, respondents are most attracted and engaged in lifestyle branding that activates through Instagram, Tiktok, Twitter and Youtube. From those social media platforms, respondents felt it was

easy to get to know the Exsport brand, knew the products being sold, were interested in ongoing promotions or discounts, and felt relevant to the Exsport brand. Therefore, it is very necessary for Exsport to make mapping and plotting for goals and content objectives that are planned on each owned Exsport social media because respondents who represent as customers have social media preferences that they use to find information with the Exsport brand. In addition, it is also possible to maximize collaboration on paid media and earned media, whether collaborating with media, individuals or with other brands. To implement this, where to Leverage and improve Exsport owned social media and increase collaboration on paid media and earned media to strengthen Exsport's new brand value communication and promote the new Exsport, there are several steps that can be taken:

- (1) Identify the benefits and functions of each social media platform
- (2) Develop a strategy on each platform
- (3) Implement pillar content re-composition on existing social media platforms
- (4) Launch marketing campaigns
- (5) Consider using location-based marketing
- (6) Collaborating with brands or individuals or communities that have the same values as Export in social media activations
- (7) Invest and develop on other social media that relate to export consumers

(2) Build brand credibility and customer trust through social media

The consumer analysis from previous data gathering indicates that customers really value brand credibility as a whole, from service to product purchases. The behavior of consumers to be able to trust the Exsport brand is to look for honest reviews that are spread on online media, both on social media or e-commerce platforms. Therefore, to address this issue, Export must also focus on a social media effort strategy in building customer trust consistently by maintaining reliable, accurate and good reviews across Export social platforms. In addition, Exsport must also develop SOPs to handle customer complaints made online. To implement this, where consistently you can continue to improve brand credibility and customer trust through social media, there are several steps that can be taken:

1. Clearly communicate policies and procedures
2. Respond promptly to customer inquiries
3. Be more transparent with customers about export ideas and innovation processes in the form of brand story telling
4. Carry out real action plans from customer feedback to improve products and services
5. Improve customer satisfaction rates from reviews and testimonials
6. Take legal action to handle fraud cases using the Exsport brand name
7. Use customer data responsibly

3. Connect better with customer and prospects customer

Based on data obtained through customer analysis and several interviews with internal teams and customer samples, where building a brand that is relevant and sustainable for a long time today requires not only converting sales from the products being sold, but also building relationships and maintaining them strong relationship between brand and customer. Therefore, to address this issue, Exsport needs to increase the intensity of communication with customers and create social media activations that involve customers or their followers. To implement this, where to be able to connect better with customer and prospects customer, there are several steps that can be taken:

1. Use social listening to build customer relationships
2. Consistently implement the standard tone of voice of the Exsport brand on all social media platforms 3. Personalize customer experience
4. Share user-generated content as a form of appreciation
5. Build online communities
6. Consistency in encouraging and responding to comments or direct message
8. Increasing the intensity of communication in the form of sharing and brainstorming

4. Gather customer data and improve membership program through online

Based on data obtained through internal team interviews and consumer analysis, Exsport has implemented membership for customers but has not maximized the membership program as a form of maintaining loyal Exsport customers where customers who become members expect benefits from registering as members. To address this issue, it is very important for Exsport to use a third party to collect online customer data because Exsport's internal system is not yet capable of gathering data independently. Analysis of the data gathering that was carried out later will affect the increase in the number of membership and develop the right membership program by taking into account customer preferences and needs. To implement this, where to collect customer data to make improvements to the membership program, there are several steps that can be taken:

1. Use customer feedback surveys
2. Use customer data from point-of-scale system
3. Use customer data from social media monitoring
4. Use customer data from online reviews and testimony
5. Use customer data from all offline store on Indonesia
6. Use customer data from third party sources
7. Communicating the benefits of the membership program
8. Development of loyalty program

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Exsport brand income has reduced both before and after rebranding from prior branding. This drop in sales and poor financial performance has become a major issue for the firm, since it may result in team reduction and the closure of numerous offline outlets across Indonesia. To address this issue, it is critical for Exsport brand to shift to online and improve their Social Marketing Effort (SMME) to communicate Exsport new brand value and share awareness to customers where Exsport has become a brand that fully supports women by providing a wide range of product, as a lifestyle brand. In order to achieve new brand equity awareness and engagement that will lead to purchase intention that will make sales increased, a comprehensive SMME strategy should be implemented. In order to properly target and position the brand in the market, it should also incorporate segmentation, targeting, and positioning (STP) analysis, marketing mix analysis, and value proposition analysis. Furthermore, the Exsport brand should focus on creating trust with customers by improving customer service and implementing a good membership program in order to collect important consumer profiles. This data can then be used to identify trends and areas for improvement, leading to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty.

The proposed SMME strategy includes leveraging and improving Exsport owned social media, increasing collaboration on paid and earned media, building brand credibility and customer trust through social media, connecting better with customers and prospects, gathering customer data, and improving the membership program online. The author also makes the Objective Key Result (OKR) point as an objectives and aim for the relevant key success indicator of the strategies. The SMME strategy will be executed over the course of six months, with detailed action plans and activities in place to achieve the intended goals. Here are some points on how to implement the proposed rebranding strategies for Exsport brand:

1. Leverage and improving Exsport owned media and increase collaboration activation on all key digital media: Utilize Exsport social media platforms includes Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, and Youtube to communicate promotion, product knowledge, product launching, collaboration campaign, and inform membership program which also supported by collaboration with KOL or influencer to grow brand audience and increase brand awareness and engagement.
2. Build brand credibility and customer trust: Improvement of brand communication with customer via media social to address complaints and questions through provide excellent service on online media by improve customer service. This movement expected to make an increase online customer rate through good ratings, review, and testimonial.
3. Connect better with customer and prospects customer: The effort that the new Export will do in order to support the strengthen the new Export brand identity and value organically, online community is one of the steps that must be achieved because this method is quite effective to implement.

4. Gather customer data and improve membership program through media social: This is in progress being implemented by Exsport, but still needs to be improved and developed to get maximum and sustainable output. Exsport has also not improved its online collective customer data system, meanwhile Exsport's customers are numerous and their profiles need to be analyzed and grouped so that Exsport can continue to improve its marketing strategy and business.

To implement those strategies, it will be important to set clear key objective and goals, and supervised and monitor through weekly checklist that will lead to agility to do improvisation and searching for alternative tactical on daily operational. It may also be helpful to seek the help of a marketing professional third party to ensure that the strategies are implemented effectively and efficiently.

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